

Crossing the Rubicon: Decision-making, Ambiguity and Dystopia in *Dune* and *Armored Core VI*

1. Introduction

If you ask a search engine on the Internet to look for the keywords „Armored Core VI Dune“, you are likely to find two hits: A thread on reddit¹ pointing out the obvious similarity between *Dune* and *Armored Core VI (AC6)* regarding the main source of both narratives, and an article on Screen Rant² offering a short text on the very same idea that *AC6* is heavily influenced by *Dune*. Eric Huels, the author of the Screen Rant article, notes that *AC6*'s influence on *Dune* is not that noteworthy, since Frank Herbert's novel „is one of the most famous pieces of science fiction ever made, so it isn't particularly revelatory that *Armored Core VI* will draw inspiration from it“.

So yes, there are striking similarities in the disposition of the two stories: Both feature a futuristic society ruled by more or less corrupt, or at least self-centered, factions fighting for control of a powerful substance that can only be harvested on a single planet. In both stories, the substance is used both as a resource for an industrial complex and as a drug³, as it alters and enhances human abilities. To operate an Armored Core (AC), a human must undergo a dangerous surgical procedure („augmentation“) that often results in the patient's death.⁴ Exposure to an extreme amount of Coral seems to allow some generations of „augmented humans“ to communicate with the Coral.⁵ Similarly, in order to fully grasp the power of the spice, one must

¹ See https://www.reddit.com/r/armoredcore/comments/zhel3k/possible_dune_inspiration_in_ac6/. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

² See <https://screenrant.com/armored-core-6-dune-frank-herbert-fromsoftware/>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

³ See „Comm's Record: Doser Ravings“.

⁴ The process is shown briefly in *AC6*'s story trailer (Bandai Namco Entertainment America 2023), and elaborated about in different in-game AC profiles, see: https://armoredcore.fandom.com/wiki/Human_PLUS#ARMORED_CORE_VI_FIRES_OF_RUBICON. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁵ See Monologue after Mission „Ocean Crossing“.

undergo a procedure that involves drinking the „water of life,“ the bile of a sandworm, usually resulting in certain death.⁶ Both stories feature worms in one way or another, be it the sandworms in *Dune* or the Coral-powered ice worm in *AC6*.

Dune and *AC6* deal heavily with transhumanism and how the enhancement of the human body and mind leads to the need to reevaluate both the benefits and, even more so, the drawbacks of such an endeavor.

Both stories could be told under the label of „environmental dystopia“, as they aim at the plot of a negative utopia, in which the over-exploitation of a planet and its ability to provide humanity with its resources strongly determines the future of this very humanity, a future that the player or reader most likely won't be eager to have anyway, as it is dominated by war, betrayal and death.

But it is not only on the thematic level that the two works are similar. In this paper, I want to explore the similarities of *Dune* and *AC6* in the way moral ambiguity and decision making are designed along the major endings (*AC6*) and narrative strands (*Dune*). I hope to show that the ways in which decisions are negotiated are very similar, thus proving not only an influence of *Dune* as a sci-fi masterpiece, but also in how it establishes markers for moral decision making - or confronts the reader/player with the downsides of their choices. Ironically, the focus on choice also fits well with *Dune's* narrative, which relies heavily on the idea that different versions of the future are available to those who can master the spice high: Paul Atreides in his Mua'dib form as well as Leto II. are presented with a plethora of options that lead to different outcomes, and they are confronted with making serious decisions based on these visions.⁷ The decision tree is therefore not only interesting to look at for the development of *Dune's* and *AC6's* story, but also as an actual narrative element itself.

⁶ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n607>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁷ E.g. see <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n255>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

2. Dune and Armored Core VI

2.1 Visionary reflection and heavy decision-making: *Dune*

Dune is one of the most influential science fiction novels, but remained relatively marginal until Denis Villeneuve released his first movie based on the first half of the first book of *Dune*, which consists of six books that can be considered canon, as they cover the main storylines and were written by Frank Herbert himself. Although it probably influenced most sci-fi works, compared to Star Wars, Star Trek, or other commercially successful franchises, *Dune* was less present in popular culture outside of its own fandom community.

In this paper, I will not cover the entire history of *Dune*, not even the six books I just called canon. Instead, I will focus only on the first three books, which contain the story of Paul Atreides up to his actual death and the beginning of the metamorphosis of his son Leto II. This part of the canon is a final story that ends with a gap of several thousand years until the beginning of the plot of the fourth book, most of the main characters remain alive or present until the end of the third book.

The story basically follows the development of the noble Atreides dynasty, a feudal house that rules over the planet Caladan, which is rich in water, fauna, and green flora. As part of a galactic empire under the rule of an emperor from the House of Corinno, they are given the planet Arrakis to govern and ensure the exploitation and export of its main resource: Spice. Spice is a powerful resource that can be used to expand one's consciousness and is, among other things, responsible for humanity's ability to travel through space: The so-called „Navigators“, degenerate humans who have consumed too much spice, are able to see through time and space, thus ensuring safe space travel without the danger of a ship suddenly crashing on a random planet

along the way.⁸ Space travel is organized by the Space Guild, a powerful economic entity that is not under the Emperor's command, but is highly dependent on a fluid spice income.

Before the Atreides took over Arrakis, the planet was ruled by House Harkonnen, who are portrayed as the antithesis of the Atreides: Their leaders and personnel are described as evil and brutal, willing to exploit, enslave, or kill anyone who gets in their way.⁹ The third and probably most important party is the local indigenous population: The Fremen. They are at home in the desert, organized in tribal communities in „sietches“, secure camps, often located in rock formations that hide them from the harsh desert conditions. The Fremen depend on the spice not only for their economic survival, but also for their physical addiction.

The Fremen believe in Shai Hulud, the god-like form of a sand worm (or the collective of sand worms). Arrakis is home to giant sand worms that threaten anyone who moves through the desert. These worms are part of the life cycle of the spice, as without the worm there would be no spice.¹⁰ In addition, the Fremen believe in a messianic figure, a savior called Kwisatz Haderakh.

Shortly after settling on Arrakis, the Atreides are betrayed and attacked by the Harkonnen army with the help of the Emperor's special unit, the Sardaukar, as the Emperor fears the power of the Atreides.¹¹ While Leto I, head of the house, is killed, his son Paul and his mother Jessica are able to escape into the desert, where they find refuge with a rebellious Fremen tribe. Paul is increasingly believed by the Fremen to be the Kwisatz Haderach, as he responds well to drinking the „Water of Life“ and is able to awaken the Fremen's hope for liberation from the

⁸ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n623>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁹ The „evil old Baron“ (<https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n255>, accessed 10 Apr. 2024) tells his son Rabban „the beast“ (<https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n57>, accessed 10 Apr. 2024.) to „show now mercy“ in ruling Arrakis (<https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n301>, accessed 10 Apr. 2024.).

¹⁰ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n645>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

¹¹ One could very much question, why they are given *Dune* in the first place, the story suggests that it was only given to them so the plot against them could be carried out successfully as for the lacking support of Arrakis and the natural enmity of the Fremen against any colonial ruler.

colonial rule of the now reborn Harkonnen. Jessica, who is part of a mystical sisterhood that plans to create the Kwisatz Haderach with a strict breeding policy among the feudal houses, herself plays the role of the savior's mother and becomes the „Reverend Mother“, a shaman-like matriarch for the tribe.

With the power of his visions and the strong religious narrative that he is the prophesied savior, Paul, who now calls himself „Muad'dib,“ is able to unite the Fremen tribes under his banner. With the control of sand worms, which can be ridden with a special Fremen technique, and the use of nuclear weapons, he is finally able to destroy the emperor-backed Harkonnen rule and even claim the Emperor's throne.

Muad'dib's reign is followed by the creation of a church to support the religious base and consolidate Paul's power. However, the prophesied prosperity turns out to destroy the planet's ecosystem: The worms cannot live in the terraformed parts of Arrakis, so the growth of spices, the basis of any rule in the *Dune* universe, decreases. The religious system partially collapses when Paul is blinded by a rebellious nuclear attack and eventually leaves the city to die in the desert, in awe of the fundamentalist religious system he and/or his followers have created around him. His sister Aliya succeeds him as leader of the churches and manifests the fundamentalist character, now able to rely on the myth of Paul's messianic nature.

In the final book, members of the House of Corinno attempt to regain power over Arrakis by assassinating Paul's children, Leto II and Ghanima. They survive the attempts to take their lives and find refuge among rebellious Fremen, who are initially skeptical of the children's goals, having seen the results of the Atreides' supposedly righteous rule: A planet with a dying ecosystem, fewer worms, Fremen who have forgotten their origins and are ruled by a fundamentalist, absolutist regime. Finally, they decide to follow Leto II against the corrupted regime, and with the help of allies among the Corinno's and the reappearance of Paul, who has renounced all prophetic claims and presents himself only as a blind preacher, they are able to reconquer Arrakis and re-establish a second reign of the Atreides (lasting for 4000 years), now under the rule of Leto II, who, unlike his father, has chosen the path of a theocratic tyranny.

An important issue in the narrative of *Dune* is the question of decision making. No decision made by a character is simply described as right or wrong. There is a strong sense of ambiguity in the development of the story. The mystical element of the spice rush contributes to this, as it allows the consumer to see all possible options with their full consequences. In one scene, Paul sits in a tent with his mother and has a vision that shows him all the evil that his decision will bring upon humanity, forcing him to consider whether the decision he is about to make is indeed the right one.¹² Later, when Leto II. confronts Paul in a similar situation, Paul makes a clear case that he does not want his son to make the same decision that he did, as he struggled mightily with the consequences. Leto II, however, is willing to deal with the pain he will cause for a greater good, the survival of humankind, by choosing the theocracy as God's emperor.¹³

Reflection is generally a recurring theme in *Dune*, pages, and pages of the characters' thoughts on certain developments, decisions to be made, the consequences, and whether they are worth it. Thus, the narrative of *Dune* is heavily influenced by the decisions of its characters. Herbert himself addressed the issues of power and decision-making in his essay *Dune Genesis*: „Enormous problems arise when human mistakes are made on the grand scale available to a superhero“¹⁴.

2.2 Money or moral: Decision-making in Armored Core

Armored Core VI is the latest installment of the Armored Core series, developed by the Japanese studio From Software, and features fast-paced third person mecha gameplay combined with a wide variety of build options and a mission-based narrative style. It is independent from previous editions, although some themes are loosely related to previous games.¹⁵ As such, I will generally treat it as a standalone game with its own world-building and narrative structure.

¹² See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n255>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

¹³ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n1193>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

¹⁴ Herbert 1980.

¹⁵ E.g. the „augmentation“ was former referred to as „Human Plus“, Coral was introduced as a new facet of that process, see https://armoredcore.fandom.com/wiki/Human_PLUS#ARMORED_CORE_VI_FIRES_OF_RUBICON. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

The story revolves around a mercenary AC with the number 621. Its missions are managed by a handler called „Handler Walter“. The missions take place on the planet Rubicon III, which is the only place in space where a resource called Coral can be harvested. Several Corporations are fighting each other for the best position in the exploitation of the planet's resource, while a rebel group called the „Rubicon Liberation Front“ (RLF) is fighting to liberate the planet from the Corporations. Another faction, the Planetary Closure Administration (PCA), is introduced as an overarching enemy that seeks to consolidate singular power over the planet under its rule.

At first, 621 is assigned to missions for three companies, with no preference or allegiance. This changes at the beginning of the second chapter. 621 learns of the existence of a character named „Cinder Carla“, „Cinder“ referring to someone who survived the Fires of Ibis.¹⁶ Carla, as well as the Rubicon Liberation Front, are now increasingly trying to win the loyalty of the 621 in their fight against the Corporations. In the mission „Attack the Watchpoint“, 621 must destroy a reactor core and is exposed to a massive concentration of Coral. From this point on, 621 hears the female voice of a being called Ayre, who tells them about the true nature of the Coral: That the Coral is not a resource, but rather a living thing, a collective of „brothers and sisters“¹⁷ that can make everyone benefit from its presence if it is allowed to flourish.

With the emergence of the PCA, the Corporations agree to a truce to defeat its most powerful weapon: a giant metal worm powered by Coral. With the defeat of the PCA, one Corporation succeeds in gaining absolute power over the planetary military and harvesting infrastructure, leaving the Liberation Front and the Coral as the remaining opposing forces. As if that were not enough, Carla and Walter now open to the player and reveal their own involvement with a group called „The Overseers“. This group is dedicated to ensuring that the devastating potential of the Coral is contained, which ultimately means that the Coral must be destroyed before it can unleash itself through exponential growth. Since the Corporations are unwilling or

¹⁶ See Briefing of Mission „Ocean Crossing“.

¹⁷ See Monologue after the Mission „Destroy the Ice Worm“.

unable to see the danger of such an event, the Overseers are now the adversaries of every other group: The Coral and the Liberation Front, as well as the Corporations.

621 must decide which faction to side with, leading to different endings for the story: If they choose to side with the Overseers, the Corporation's harvesting facilities and the powerful AC form of Ayre are to be destroyed, resulting in the end of Coral growth and exploitation by „igniting“ a massive Coral explosion, thus the „Fires of Raven“ ending. If they choose to side with Ayre, the Coral explosion is avoided. This ending occurs along with the liberation of Rubicon from the Corporations and is therefore referred to as the „Liberator of Rubicon“ ending.

If the player plays through the story three times in a row, the story changes on the third playthrough. An AI called „Allmind“, introduced in the first playthrough to provide the player with training modes for various boss encounters (the „Arena“), gains momentum and serves as a new client. Whatever the player's decision in the first two playthroughs, Ayre becomes increasingly skeptical of Allmind's ambitions in the third. She tells the player about data records she has discovered that can be linked to Allmind's activities. These lead to new challenges in the arena and ultimately to a completely different endgame in which Allmind is revealed to have convinced AC pilots to support its cause. If 621 chooses to side with the AI, they become the final step in Allmind's ultimate plan: A Coral release.

„Coral Release“ describes the explosion of a critical mass of Coral and its distribution throughout the universe. It is the exact opposite of the Overseer ending, leading not to the destruction of all Coral, but to its release into the universe. The final cutscene of the „Alea Iacta Est“ ending is the most apocalyptic, as the release destroys much of the infrastructure managed and used by humans, leading to a reawakening of the surviving tech under Coral control: The very resource that was the object of exploitation becomes the subject of the exploiter.

Thus, *AC6* has three endings that place different emphasis on different perspectives of liberation, either the liberation of all humanity from the danger of the Corals, or the liberation of the galaxy from human domination. The „Liberator of the Rubicon“ ending offers a compromise

in a way, as Ayre supposedly aims to find a way for human-Coral coexistence in this specific ending.

The story of AC weighs heavily on the issue of free will. There are several levels where this becomes visible. The most obvious one is probably the development of 621 from being „handled“ by Walter, named, and framed as a dog,¹⁸ to a self-determined, independent mercenary or even freedom fighter, whose decisions are no longer based on the financial outcome, but rather on what is morally right or wrong. In the tutorial mission, 621 must pick up a license to be able to participate in the mercenary business on Rubicon III. A working license found on a destroyed AC is commissioned under the call sign „Raven“. This is a foreshadowing, because as the story develops, it becomes clear that „Raven“ is not a random call sign, but rather a title associated with an independent actor. YouTuber FatBrett points out in their story analysis that „Raven mercenaries champion free will,¹⁹ which includes not only physical strength, but also the strength to stand up for their choices. As the story progresses, 621 becomes more and more independent of Walter's leadership, and eventually must decide who to support. During the mission „Defend the Old Spaceport“, in which the „original“ Raven tries to kill 621, the communication goes like this: The enemy operator acknowledges that „this mercenary [621] has potential“. Ayre continues: „... the will to choose.“

In the end, the element of choice is not just a level of interaction for the player to choose from different missions, but an integral part of the lore around 621, implemented and made accessible by offering choices in mission design that affect the endings. The act of choice itself is transferred to the player through the game's interaction design, emphasizing the difficulty of choice, as will be discussed later.

¹⁸ E.g. see the video essay by Absurd (2023) on the topic of dehumanization in AC6's language.

¹⁹ See FatBrett 2023.

3. The question of the right decision: Defend, Destroy or Unleash?

As we have seen, the narratives of *AC6* and *Dune* rely heavily on the idea of independence and the human capacity for free will and choice. While we could simply accept this as a common theme, I would like to delve deeper into the final choices of *AC6* and compare them to the possible choices and decisions made by Paul Atreides/Muad'dib. I will argue that both narratives share a similar perspective on the idea of how to introduce morality, consequence, and free will into the decision-making process, especially in cases that have a major impact on the environment and society in which the decision is made.

There are basically three types of decisions that can be made: To defend, to defeat, or to liberate. The first, defense, is related to the idea of protecting something valuable from foreign exploitation. It is the basic anticolonial idea of resistance against an oppressor. The second, defeat, is characterized by the idea that destroying something, even if it is precious, is better than letting it fall into the wrong hands because of the incalculable risks involved. The third, unleashing, is the exact opposite of the first, meaning the extreme and violent distribution of the precious element to simply overwhelm the environment with it and thus gain the upper hand by sheer numbers.

3.1 Defense

In *AC6*, the defense choice is embedded in the „Liberator of Rubicon“ ending. 621 must choose against the Overseers and side with Ayre, who must kill the Overseers' ACs and destroy the Cooperation's hold on the planet Rubicon III. The moral difficulty of this choice is that it must be made against two people who are portrayed as friendly and supportive: Carla and Walter. After Carla rescues 621 from the Corporations, she and Walter reveal their goal: to destroy the Coral and thus end the War on Coral. No one will win.

However, Ayre, herself a Coral being, explains to 621 that this would not only mean the end of the Coral War, but also the end of her „family“²⁰. Coral is portrayed as a living collective, and Ayre increasingly personifies it, creating the idea that the Overseers' plan is genocide rather than simply the destruction of a (dead) resource being fought over. She describes it as „burning to extinction,“²¹ again referring to Coral as something that lives and can die. 621 must make the decision, and if they side with Ayre, they must kill Carla and Walter before they can carry out their plan to provoke a Coral explosion.

But beyond the moral question of siding with an indigenous lifeform to prevent its extinction, Ayre also appeals to 621's independent choice, making it clear that this decision is not to be influenced by 621's loyalty to Walter or any notion of obligation. She tells 621 that she is not addressing „Walter's dog, but Raven, the independent mercenary“²². Leaving aside the question of how independent a mercenary's choice is, given that this position is based on financial redemption, it is once again clear that Ayre understands this to be a matter of free will in the Kantian sense, at least in theory.

The necessity of killing Walter is also mitigated by the fact that he himself was imprisoned by the Corporations after the „Reach the Coral Convergence“ mission and returned changed. Ayre warns 621 that they are in danger, „whatever they have done“, when they face Walter,²³ and V.II Snails speaks of him as „recalcitrant to the last“²⁴. Walter himself seems to be almost dead, his voice broken, his words unclear. After he is defeated, however, the real Walter can speak one last time, acknowledging 621's victory and realizing that 621 has chosen to side with Ayre. In an almost fatherly manner, his last words are: „Look at you, 621, you found... a friend“²⁵.

In the final cutscene, it becomes clear that with the help of 621 „Raven“, the Rubicon Liberation Front can push back the Corporations and regain control of the planet and thus the Coral. As

²⁰ See Monologue after Mission „Destroy the Ice Worm“.

²¹ See Briefing of Mission „Eliminate ‘Cinder’ Carla“.

²² Ibid.

²³ See Monologue during Mission „Bring Down the Xylem“.

²⁴ See Monologue during Mission „Destroy the Drive Block“.

²⁵ See Monologue after defeating Walter in Mission „Bring Down the Xylem“.

written before, this is a clear anticolonial theme where the self-determination of an indigenous population is the ultimate goal in the struggle for freedom. Thus, this ending is probably the easiest to see as „the good ending“²⁶.

In *Dune*, the choice of defense is not addressed. Rather, it is suggested as Paul's choice in the general arc of the first book but challenged by Paul's visions of himself turning the universe into a fundamentalist battleground. Theoretically, Paul's decision to side with the Fremen, drink the Water of Life, and become their religious and military leader to destroy the colonial rule over Arrakis can be understood as a defensive decision in the same way that 621 chooses to side with the Rubiconians against the Overseers and the Corporations.

In this reading, it also becomes clear why *Dune* has been proposed as a „white savior“ story²⁷: The foreign (even white) actor hurries to the help of the oppressed people of color, who are not able to resist and win for themselves. But since the core story of Paul Atreides is not finalized in the first book, and even allows glimpses of later developments through his visions, *Dune* cannot be judged by the first book alone. Moreover, with the disempowerment of the emperor at the very end of the first book, the war on Arrakis already reaches far beyond the borders of the planet, so that even the good „Liberator“ ending is questionable.

Looking only at the characters of Paul and 621, both resemble the anticolonial freedom fighter up to the point where the corporate presence on the planet is defeated. It is easy to find sympathy for Paul in the narration of the first book of *Dune*, and to see his decision not to escape his fate as the noble and right one. It almost resembles what Frantz Fanon has described as the unification of tribes by their will to challenge the power of the oppressor, and, especially important in Paul's case: „All this is evocative of a confraternity, a church, and a mystical body of belief at one and the same time“²⁸. Given that *Dune* was published in the 1960s, a time when

²⁶ See MadLuigi 2023.

²⁷ See <https://slate.com/culture/2021/10/dune-2021-movie-vs-book-white-savior-islam.html> (Accessed 10 Apr. 2024) and Büchner 2022, pp. 66 et seq.

²⁸ See Fanon 1963, p. 133. It must be noted, though, that the anticolonial narrative is „not as progressive as this short evaluation might sound“ (Jacob 2022, p. 33), for further discussion on the topic see Jacob 2022.

the decolonization of the Arab world was well underway, this is not surprising. The religious level of unification is absent in *AC6*, but the mystical is not: 621, or Raven, actually provokes a unification of the Rubiconians under their „war cry” and is eventually suggested by Ayre to change Rubicon according to their will: „Now I want to see the future you choose”²⁹, 621 becomes, so to speak, a „Mecha Mahdī”.

To summarize: Defense means following the anticolonial paradigm that only indigenous people can decide how best to act to ensure the well-being of their people. However, given that the dangers of Coral and Spice are still present, it is questionable whether a socially and politically unstable species such as humans and Coral will be able to contain this danger in an unknown future. It may be the choice that feels „right”, especially given the sense of independence and self-determination in a post-colonial world, but the world only remains stable for so long: *Dune* is a perfect example of how a well-advised, morally „good” decision can ultimately lead to the opposite of what was intended.

3.2 Destruction

The second path that can be chosen in *AC6* is the path of destruction: Should 621 choose to side with the Overseers, they will navigate the massive spaceship Xylem into a Coral mining structure, provoking its second ignition into a destructive explosion: The „Fires of Raven”. As a result of the explosion, most life in the galaxy is destroyed, and Rubicon III is subsequently abandoned by the Corporations.

This path is interesting, as it not only highlights the idea of free will, but also the idea of 621's emancipation from their handlers, while accepting their own path as the „right” one. Throughout the story, 621 collects data logs from the researchers that preceded the „Fires of Ibis,” the first Coral explosion that nearly destroyed all Coral. It is revealed to 621 that Walter himself

²⁹ Rusty, a companion fighting alongside 621 for the RLF: „Every Rubiconian who heard your cry rose up to fight. [...] Never thought I'd be rubbing shoulders with the liberator of Rubicon”, see Mission Intro „Destroy the Drive Block”.

was the son of one of the scientist's assistants³⁰ who ignited that first Coral explosion, and Walter decided to follow in his father's footsteps to finish what he and his professor had started but couldn't.³¹

Since Walter cannot finish the job himself due to his capture by the Corporations, he hands the task over to 621. The interesting point here is that the objective of this final and devastating task is not communicated as a standard handler-to-mercenary mission, but rather as the right thing to do. Walter explains his motivation to 621, giving them the rational arguments to decide for themselves. He even addresses 621's free will by telling him: „I have one last job: Find your freedom“³². The handler has released his dog, who is now free to choose whether to join the Overseers' plan to destroy the Coral or to side with the RLF, as I discussed in the previous part of this essay.

The decision to join the Overseers' plan does not come without an immediate cost: 621 must defeat an RLF AC with the call sign „Rusty,“ who is introduced and developed as 621's „buddy,“ even though Rusty's emotional affinity is far less dense than Carla's and Walter's, and thus killing him might feel less „bad“ than killing the latter in the decision branch to side with the RLF. However, 621 also must defeat Ayre in AC form and thus must kill their companion for most of the game. In the fight, Ayre reminds the player that she wanted to create a „symbiosis“³³ between humans and Coral, thus emphasizing that the player's choice was wrong.

By naming the ensuing Coral explosion after 621's chosen title, it is made clear that it was their own responsibility to choose this path. Much as 621 „Raven“ is framed as the „Liberator of Rubicon“ in the homonymous ending, there is a strong emphasis on the events being the result of a decision based on free will. In both endings, the most decisive parties emphasize the freedom of choice that 621 has. This is also implemented in the way that both endings are reached, without the need for specific prior decisions: It is simply possible to either side with the RLF,

³⁰ Carla was probably the other assistant, see Professor Nagai's Log (3) and (5).

³¹ See Walter's message after the Mission „Reach the Coral Convergence“ (not on Allmind path).

³² Ibid.

³³ See Monologue during Mission „Shut down the closure satellites“.

kill Carla and Walter, and follow Ayre's reasoning, or side with the Overseers, kill Rusty and Ayre, and follow Carla's and Walter's reasoning.

Comparing this path to how *Dune* unfolds, it is a little more difficult to find parallels, as this is only a hypothetical potential in *Dune's* probable timelines. The Spice is known to be a threat to galactic peace, in terms of its enormous impact on the power structure of the human-run universe. However, it is *not* destroyed by either Paul Atreides/Muad'dib or Leto II, at least not in the same way and with the same reasoning as in the analogous ending of *AC6*.

However, the scenario of the total destruction of the Spice is a very realistic theme that is mentioned in two situations: First, Paul uses the threat of spice destruction against the Space Guild to force their neutrality towards the Corinno-led Empire. The guild's navigators rely heavily on the spice to navigate through space, and stopping the spice supply would essentially mean losing their power over interstellar economics and politics. Since they also have the ability to properly assess the seriousness of this issue, their decision to commit to Paul's request is a clear indication that they see it as possible.

Second, in a dialog with Chani, Paul describes the actual process of destroying all spice and the political implications of this option:

„The Water of Death,” he said. „It'd be a chain reaction.” He pointed to the floor. „Spreading death among the little makers, killing a vector of the life cycle that includes the spice and the makers. Arrakis will become a true desolation—without spice or maker.”³⁴

So, there is a potential option and path that could have led to the complete destruction of the spice. This would have led to the devastation of Arrakis, because without the spice there is no life on the planet, and intergalactic travel, economy, and thus politics would collapse. The reason why Paul didn't choose this path, instead sticking to the jihad he wanted to avoid, remains

³⁴ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n549>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

unclear, but compared to the much more ruthless Leto II, it may simply have been his inability to commit to such a devastating path of total destruction for the sake of his conscience.

The basic idea behind these paths, whether executed in *AC6* or conceived in *Dune*, is that it is better to destroy something, even if there is collateral damage, before it can become an even greater danger to humanity later. This is From Software/Herbert's version of the Trolley Problem, a (far too) basic problem in moral philosophy in which a tram driver must decide whether to cause the death of one or five men working on the tracks. The problem is also similar to the question of whether to shoot down a plane hijacked by terrorists so as not to risk more casualties, which arose in the aftermath of the September 11 attacks, and ultimately asks you to confirm or reject Bentham's utilitarian theory that an action is right: „when the tendency it has to augment the happiness of the community is greater than any it has to diminish it”³⁵.

However, From Software's, as well as Herbert's, approach to the problem is to avoid a superficial pseudo- philosophical conflict by giving a clear indication that there is no right choice: Every choice has a downside. In this way, I would refuse to frame any of the endings as „good“ or „bad,“ and instead support the gray zone tonality expressed in Paul Atreides' struggle with his own choices and paths: There is no „right“ choice in a path that branches into multiple deadly futures. And *Dune*, as well as the multiple endings in *AC6*, show very well the inevitability of these deadly futures, no matter what decision the agent will make. The powerlessness one feels when confronted with the power of decisions that have grave consequences creates a sense of unease and guilt, underscoring the dark and sinister tonality that underlies the entire cosmos of *AC6* and *Dune*, where the supposed heroes are actually just different facets of gray in an all-encompassing gray zone.³⁶

³⁵ See https://www.econlib.org/library/Bentham/bnthPML.html?chapter_num=2#book-reader and https://www.econlib.org/library/Bentham/bnthPML.html?chapter_num=5#book-reader (Accessed 10 Apr. 2024). I want to avoid discussing the case of destruction from an utilitarian perspective, though, but simply highlight a possible way to reason for it to be conceived as the „right“ choice.

³⁶ This resonates well with Herbert's aim to basically write a critique of „superheroism“, see Herbert 1980.

3.3 Unleashing

The final path to be discussed is different in that it is the only AC6 ending that is *not* presented as the result of an independent choice based on 621's free will, although the decision to submit to Allmind's will could ultimately be considered free will.

In the third playthrough, and only if the player finishes the game twice and chooses both different endings, Ayre becomes aware of suspicious activity around the AI called Allmind, the „Mercenary Support System“ that provides AC training to the player in the arena. This is an interesting twist, as there is no clear indication until the third playthrough that Allmind is anything other than an in-game framework for offering one-on-one combat against AI ACs. In a sense, a framing narrative becomes the core narrative in the third playthrough. Allmind takes the pro-Coral path and goes several steps further: It wants a Coral release to happen, essentially the very thing the Overseers want to avoid, and a proper „crossing of the Rubicon“: Coral is released into the universe, and the consequences for humanity are dire.³⁷

On the way to this ending, the endgame changes radically: If 621 chooses to side with Allmind, they basically go dark to sabotage the Overseers' plan. Along the way, it becomes clear that Allmind sees 621 as an executioner of its plan rather than an independent actor with free will,³⁸ culminating in Allmind wanting to kill 621 after all tasks are completed and the opponents of its plan are destroyed. Thus, in this final path, 621 does *not* kill their former companions themselves. It is also revealed that 621 is not the first AC Allmind has used to carry out its plans. Another AC pilot, call sign Iguazu, is introduced early in the game³⁹ as a seemingly minor AC from the same generation as 621. From their perspective, they were using Allmind to finally

³⁷ The Youtuber MadLuigi highlights the nomenclature, given that the ending is called „Alea Iacta Est“, referring to Julius' Cesar's crossing of the Rubicon river. He adds that the Kanji sign for three looks like the Roman number 3, thus creating another linking between the name of the planet Rubicon 3 to the river. The ending is thus being framed as the very „point of no return“ that is expressed by the idiom „crossing the Rubicon“. See MadLuigi 2023.

³⁸ MadLuigi points to Allmind waking 621 up by using the „cerebral Coral control device“ and 621 going along with Allmind's plan, even after defeating it. He thus questions the freedom of will, that could have led to this decision. See Ibid.

³⁹ See Mission „Attack the Dam complex“.

overpower the more successful 621, while not caring about the AI's actual plan.⁴⁰ It could also be seen the other way around, though, that Allmind was using Iguazu's stubborn will to defeat 621 to carry out its plan.

At the very end, Allmind is killed, and Ayre decides for 621 to go along with the plan to start the Coral release. This is interesting in that it presents the same perspective on the future of Coral as the RLF ending, but this time ignoring the cooperative idea of a symbiosis: 621 becomes a mere tool to realize Ayre's true plan. This is emphasized by the fact that the ending is also referred to as the „true ending“⁴¹. Since this ending is also only available after two play-throughs and after the „Liberator of Rubicon“ ending, one could assume that Ayre's plan was to free Coral after all, only that the presence of 621's own will prevented a proper release in the first timeline and decision path, forcing them to commit to a „symbiosis“ compromise.

In *Dune*, a similar phenomenon occurs with the takeover of Leto II. At the end of the second book, Paul decides to go into the desert to die, but since he returns in the third book as the blind preacher, this can be seen as the *Dune* equivalent of the concept of Ġayba⁴². His children, Leto II. and Ghanima, who were themselves exposed to massive amounts of spice before birth, grow up as entities who are children only in physical form, but inside form a mélange of all the generations that came before them, including all the generations' complete „genetic memory“⁴³. After several attempts on their lives by various actors who fear their potential power as adults, Leto II. flees into the desert. There he meets the Blind Preacher, who has appeared several times in the capital city of Arrakeen, accusing the Church of Muad'dib of ignoring the true message of Muad'dib's will. Leto II. reveals the preacher to be his father, who reluctantly follows his son on his path to reclaim the throne, this time not only as emperor and

⁴⁰ See Monologue during Mission „Coral Release“.

⁴¹ E.g. see https://www.ign.com/wikis/armored-core-6-fires-of-rubicon/How_to_Get_Every_Ending#Alea_lacta_Est_-_ALLMIND. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁴² A clear reference to the Šī'a, in which the last Imam is believed to have gone to the great absence, see MacDonald and Hodgson 2012. For further discussions of the use of Islamic terminology in *Dune* see Jacob 2022.

⁴³ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n879>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

quasi-religious leader, but as an actual god⁴⁴ Leto II. enters a symbiosis with a sandtrout, only to be transformed into one himself, thereby manifesting his power over the spice.

At the very end of Book 3, Leto II and Paul discuss the right choice. It becomes clear that Leto II is much less ruthless and willing to accept the dire consequences of a path that would allow him to take control of the empire and the entire universe. It is a true „crossing of the Rubicon“:

Each of them had only a desperate and lonely courage upon which to rely, but Leto possessed two advantages: he had committed himself upon a path from which there was no turning back, and he had accepted the terrible consequences to himself. His father still hoped there was a way back and had made no final commitment.⁴⁵

Leto II. continues a path that Paul wanted to avoid by going into the desert,⁴⁶ taking on the role of the bringer of „Kralizec“⁴⁷, the ultimate storm that will destroy and purify the universe, an apocalyptic renewal called the „Golden Path“⁴⁸. Leto II. is the embodiment of an apocalyptic unleashing of power on Arrakis based on the spice, he is „Kralizec embodied“⁴⁹.

In a way, the *Dune* path of unleashing is less obvious and less directly related to Spice, but rather its product in the form of the post-metamorphosis god-emperor Leto II. as a theocratic tyrant. However, both paths follow the idea of free will up to the point where the actor decides to follow the path - be it 621's commitment to Allmind's plan or Leto II's commitment to the „Golden Path“. After this decision, the path dominates and restricts the freedom of choice, thus limiting the protagonists to mere executors. Furthermore, both paths involve a form of tyranny

⁴⁴ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n1245>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁴⁵ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n1191>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁴⁶ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n857> et seq. and <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n1071>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁴⁷ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n1241>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁴⁸ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n1193> and the introduction to book 4: <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n1263>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

⁴⁹ See <https://archive.org/details/frank-herberts-dune-saga-collection-books-1-6-by-frank-herbert/page/n1241>. Accessed 10 Apr. 2024.

and total control: The unleashing of Coral in *AC6* comes with the tyrannical version of Ayre's plan of Coral's emancipation from humanity. There is no more talk of symbiosis and coexistence, after the defeat of Allmind, Ayre directs 621 to continue Allmind's plan. The unleashing of Spice's total control over humanity comes in the form of the theocratic tyrant Leto II, who claims the title of God-Emperor, thus surpassing the claim to rule the Empire in an eschatological manner.

4. Conclusion

As we have seen, there is no „right“ choice. Depending on one's perspective, defense can be understood as the closest thing to morally clear, at least if the criterion for a decision being the „right“ one is grounded in an anticolonial idea of a population's independence from exploitation and foreign rule. It can also only be understood as „right“ if the sacrifices along the way are understood as necessary and the path to be judged ends with liberation itself. Finally, the defensive path reduces the scope and thus the criteria for success to the environment in which it takes place: Rubicon III and Arrakis. It has no effect on the rest of the universe. As *Dune* shows, liberation may not be the end of the story, the „right“ decision may very well lead to further destruction.

Both stories, *Dune* and *AC6*, rely on the three forms of decision making that I have outlined in this paper. Beyond the obvious similarities and influences in their worldbuilding, the element of how decisions are negotiated and framed, how the effects of decisions are narrated, and how this influences the development of the plot and narrative structure share common characteristics.

Finally, both stories have very specific ways of framing these choices in a dystopian, hopeless way that creates anxiety. No decision is clearly marked as the „right“ one, none of the many ways in which the story could unfold is free from ambiguity. Thus, *AC6*, like *Dune*, is quite capable of forcing the reader or player to confront themselves with the ambiguity of the consequences of possible choices: Nothing is simply good, especially in a world and time beyond our

control. And in this way, both stories almost resemble a kind of cosmic horror in which, in the end, whatever decision is made, there is no certainty that it will not escalate into chaos. To conclude this paper, I would like to quote Frank Herbert's address to a core problem in *Dune*, which describes *AC6*'s narrative just as well in emphasizing the gray zone and the dangers of unilateral decision making:

Beneath the hero's facade you will find a human being who makes human mistakes. Enormous problems arise when human mistakes are made on the grand scale available to a superhero. And sometimes you run into another problem.

It is demonstrable that power structures tend to attract people who want power for the sake of power and that a significant proportion of such people are imbalanced-in a word, insane.⁵⁰

⁵⁰ Herbert 1980.

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